

Studies on the Synthesis and Antimicrobial Properties of Aryl Barbituryl Sulphones

S. S. SHRIMALI and B. C. JOSHI*

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

and

D. KISHORE

Department of Chemistry, Banasthali University, Banasthali-304 022

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The sulphonamides (7-10) were synthesised and rearranged in concentrated H_2SO_4 to the corresponding sulphones (11-14). Structures of the compounds were established and their antimicrobial properties studied.

THE antimicrobial, antimalarial and antileprotic properties of sulphones are well-known^{1,2}. Arenesulphonamides are known to undergo rearrangement in concentrated H_2SO_4 to yield the sulphones³⁻⁶. The derivatives of salicylic acid and barbituric acid form an integral part of a large number of therapeutically important materials⁷. In the present paper this rearrangement reaction was used to convert the arenesulphonamides bearing medicinally potent⁸ salicylic¹⁰ and barbituric acids (7-10) to the corresponding sulphones (11-14).

3-Carboxy-4-hydroxybenzene sulphonyl chloride and 3-carboxy-4-hydroxy-5-nitrobenzene sulphonyl chloride were treated with *p*-toluidine to give the corresponding sulphonamides 1 and 2, which were converted to their acetyl derivatives 3 and 4 before being treated with diethyl bromomalonate to yield 5 and 6, respectively. Reaction of 5 and 6 with urea gave barbituric acid derivatives 7 and 8 and with thiourea gave thiobarbituric acid derivatives 9 and 10. Rearrangement of the sulphonamides (7-10) was effected in concentrated H_2SO_4 to yield the corresponding sulphones (11-14) (Scheme 1).

The analytical data of the compounds are presented in Table 1.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Pmr spectra ($CDCl_3$) (taken at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow) were recorded on a Varian A60D spectrometer using TMS as internal reference standard. Microanalytical data for nitrogen and sulphur were found satisfactory. The sulphonamides (1 and 2) and their acetyl derivatives (3 and 4) were prepared by known procedures^{2,4,6}.

N-(Dicarboethoxy)methyl-*N*-(4)-tolyl-3-carbomethoxy-4-hydroxy-5-nitrobenzene sulphonamide (6) : To *N*-(4)-tolyl-4-acetoxy-3-carbomethoxy-5-nitro-

Scheme 1

benzene sulphonamide (4; 4 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in dioxane (30 ml), were added bromomalonate (2.40 g, 0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (2 g) and the mixture was refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was poured into ice-water (100 ml) containing concentrated HCl (5 ml). The precipitated white solid

TABLE 1—PMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Mol. formula	Aromatic protons ArH	COOH ₂	OH/enolic OH	Phenolic OH	COOCH ₃	COOH ₂	COH ₂ of COOCH ₂ H ₂	ArNH
5	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ NS	6.6-8.1 (7H,m)	2.35 (3H,s)	4.9 (1H,b)	5.35 (1H,b)	4.05(s) -3H	4.0 (2H,q)	1.0 (3H,t)	—
6	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₁₁ N ₂ S	6.6-8.1 (6H,m)	2.35 (3H,s)	4.9 (1H,b)	5.35 (1H,b)	4.05(s) -3H	4.0 (2H,q)	1.0 (3H,t)	—
7	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₈ N ₂ S	6.8-7.8 (7H,m)	2.35 (3H,s)	6.5-6.8 (1H,b)	5.35 (1H,b)	—	—	—	—
8	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₁₀ N ₂ S	6.8-7.8 (6H,m)	2.35 (3H,s)	6.5-6.8 (1H,b)	5.35 (1H,b)	—	—	—	—
9	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₂ S ₂	6.8-7.8 (7H,m)	2.35 (3H,s)	6.5-6.8 (1H,b)	5.40 (1H,b)	—	—	—	—
10	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₉ N ₂ S ₂	6.8-7.8 (6H,m)	2.35 (3H,s)	6.5-6.8 (1H,b)	5.40 (1H,b)	—	—	—	—
11	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₈ N ₂ S	6.8-7.5 (6H,m)	2.40 (3H,s)	6.5-6.8 (1H,b)	5.35 (1H,b)	—	—	—	10.2 (1H,b)
12	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₁₀ N ₂ S	6.8-7.5 (5H,m)	2.40 (3H,s)	6.5-6.8 (1H,b)	5.35 (1H,b)	—	—	—	10.2 (1H,b)
13	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₇ N ₂ S ₂	6.8-7.5 (6H,m)	2.40 (3H,s)	6.5-6.8 (1H,b)	5.40 (1H,b)	—	—	—	10.2 (1H,b)
14	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₉ N ₂ S ₂	6.8-7.5 (5H,m)	2.40 (3H,s)	6.5-6.8 (1H,b)	5.40 (1H,b)	—	—	—	10.2 (1H,b)

was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to give needles of **6** (4.2 g, 86%), m.p. 198°.

The same procedure was followed to prepare **5** (3.9 g, 83%), m.p. 206°.

N-(5)Barbituryl-*N*-(4)-tolyl-3-carboxy-4-hydroxy-5-nitrobenzene sulphonamide (**8**): Sodium (2.2 g) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (25 ml) and to it **6** (5 g, 0.0095 mol) was added. Urea (0.60 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in hot absolute ethanol (25 ml) was then added to the above solution. The mixture was refluxed for 7 h. It was then poured into warm (50°) water (200 ml), acidified with HCl and left overnight. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol-water mixture as needles of **8** (3.8 g, 79.5%), m.p. 145°.

The same procedure was used to prepare **7** (3.2 g, 78%), m.p. 199°; **9** (3.1 g, 75%), m.p. 123°; and **10** (3.4 g, 73%), m.p. 135°.

[3-Carboxy-4-hydroxy-5-nitro]phenyl-[5-methyl-2-(5-barbiturylamino)]phenyl sulphone (**12**): The sulphonamide **8** (4.8 g, 0.01 mol) dissolved in concentrated H₂SO₄ (10 ml) was heated on a steam-bath for 10 min when the mixture acquired dark brown-red colour. It was cooled and then poured into ice-water (100 ml). The resulting light yellow solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol-water mixture to give **12** as amorphous solid (1.5 g, 31%), m.p. 266°d.

The same procedure was used to prepare **11** (1.30 g, 30%), m.p. 261°d; **13** (1.25 g, 28%), m.p. 251° and **14** (1.2 g, 25%), m.p. 241°.

Antibacterial activity: Antibacterial activity of compounds **7-14** was studied against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus viridan*, *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumonia* in 300 µg/disc by disc-diffusion method⁸. A comparison of the antimicrobial

activity of all the compounds (Table 2) examined suggests the following conclusions. Sulphones were found to be more active as compared to their isomeric sulphonamides. The presence of nitro group was found to decrease the activity of the sulphonamide and the sulphone. Sulphonamides **9** and **10** showed better antimicrobial activity than **7** and **8**, which could be due to the presence of sulphur of the thiobarbituric acid moiety. Sulphone **13** showed the maximum activity, which could be attributed to the presence of thiobarbituric acid moiety and also the absence of the nitro group in the molecule.

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY DATA* OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. viridan</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>K. pneumonia</i>
7	±	∓	∓	—
8	∓	—	∓	—
9	+	±	+	±
10	±	∓	±	∓
11	+	—	+	—
12	±	∓	∓	∓
13	++	+	+	+
14	+	±	±	±

* (-) = <7 mm, (+) = 11-13 mm, (∓) = 7-9 mm, (++) = 13-15 mm, (±) = 9-11 mm.

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